

Take Home Message: “Med-CORDEX new activity session”

Bodo Ahrens, Samuel Somot

- Med-CORDEX is a “open club” of climate modellers and users
 - Launching new relevant modelling activities in Med-CORDEX is possible at any time
 - You just need a small group of motivated participants, a clear concept and the “GO” of the Steering Committee
 - Different structures are possible: task team, FPS, impact modelling team, writing team
 - You can propose new ideas to the community to start gathering interested persons (medcordex@meteo.fr)
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- **Med. Paleoclimate** - past centuries to past millennia (E. Xoplaki et al.): learning from the past via proxies (seasonality, interannual variability, ...), interest for different temporal foci and coupled modelling with high spatial resolution (with open Dardanelles i.e. with Black Sea); common protocol tbd; no paleo.competition in CORDEX=>probably highly welcome by CORDEX SAT; more groups invited. Contact point: Elena Xoplaki
 - **Ocean stand-alone climate modelling** (Jebnoun & Harzallah, Jorda et al.): sensitivity to different atm. and atlantic forcings; suggestion: focus on sensitivity to atlantic forcing (T, S, and formulation of the buffer zone). Various groups running ocean stand-alone configurations but no clear interest for a coordinated activity. Needs coordination/coordinator and shaping common scientific questions for the group if we want to re-start something. Contact point: Gabriel Jorda
 - **Seasonal to decadal forecast.** We wait for the response for a related COST action Contact point: Bodo Ahrens
 - **Storyline approach** (Mindlin, Cardoso’s talk, Coppola, Shepherd, Somot): tool to pick the CMIP6 sims which fit (selection criteria in add. to quality); Start for the known storylines (Zappa, Shepherd, SSS Atl change,) and define new ones (Atl SL change) for the Med region. Possibility to become a MyClimateRisk regional hub. Contact point: Samuel Somot
 - **Coastal risks** -> special session
 - **Biogeochemistry** -> special session
 - Other ideas ? -> nothing more identified during the session